

ISic4418

Epitaph for [-?-], child of Gerontios

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

plinth

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited site

Last Change

2020-05-28 - Jonathan Prag created the file from template, publications, and photographs

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Tomb 80 of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa , where it remains in situ

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Necropoli di Abakainon

Physical Description

Plinth (support for a stele) with mouldings top and bottom, of the local sandstone; the upper part of the plinth is heavily damaged, with all of the upper portion missing and the left corner heavily damaged; only the lower portion of the text-bearing face is preserved. The plinth is the right one of a pair mounted on a single base, classified as an epitymbion of type C.

Dimensions

Height 29 cm

Width 49 cm

Depth 63.5 cm

Layout

Most of the lower line of Greek text is preserved, centred on the front face of the plinth; traces of a preceding line are visible.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neat, regular, simply cut, widely spaced letters. Epsilon has shorter middle bar; rho has closed, regular eye; omicron is small and mid-line; nu is broad with verticals of equal length.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 59 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not recorded mm

Text

1. [---]ς

2. Ἐρόντιου

Apparatus

text based upon photographs

Sofia 2018: [-----]; a horizontal is visible above the final ou of line 2, which in context is surely the remains of a final sigma (the stone shows no traces of further letters to the right).

Sofia 2018: [Γ]εροντιου; the foot of a vertical stroke is clearly visible before the epsilon, and the spacing is most compatible with Γ.

Translation (en)

[?] (child) of Gerontios

Commentary

Interpretation of this fragmentary text is context dependent. The text/plinth forms a pair with the adjoining plinth ISic4417 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4417>]. On that second plinth, the genitive [---]εροντιου is legible in the second line. The only attested Greek name compatible with this is Γερόντιος [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%93%CE%B5%CF%81%CF%8C%CE%BD%CF%84%CE%B9%CE%BF%CF%82], which is known in later Roman times at Catania (ISic3199 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3199>]) and Syracuse (Orsi 1896 [<https://www.zotero.org/groups/isicily/items/H73GNMU6>] : 31 no.318) - and the restoration of a gamma at the start of line 2 of the text presented here is the obvious resolution of the traces visible on the stone. Comparison with other examples of paired monuments in this necropolis, particularly ISic4415 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4415>] / ISic4416 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4416>], shows that these monuments can record siblings. It is therefore all but certain that we can restore the name Γερόντιος in line 2 of both ISic4417 and this text, and that these two plinths also record siblings. In a few cases, including ISic4415/ISic4416 and ISic1208 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1208>], the first name is presented in the nominative: the traces of a horizontal at the end of line 1 visible on this stone strongly suggest a final sigma, which is most likely a nominative termination (although genitive forms are also possible).

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

- Bacci, G.M., Coppolino, P. 2009. La Necropoli di Abakainon: primi dati. Messina. At 113 and 166 tav.XXXIVa
- Sofia, G. 2015. Abakainon. Nella dimora di Ade. La necropoli in contrada Cardusa a Tripi. Terme Vigliatore (ME). At 113 fig.115
- Sofia, G. 2018. Nuove iscrizioni funerarie dalla necropoli di Abakainon. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 206: 103-112. At 107 no.8 and fig.9

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